

TILSHUNOSLIKNING AMALIY MASALALARI: ZAMONAVIY TILSHUNOSLIKNING DOLZARB MUAMMOLARI, YECHIMLARI, TARAQQIYOTI VA ISTIQBOLLARI

mavzusidagi xalqaro ilmiy-amaliy anjuman

MATERIALLARI

2025-yil 29-30-sentabr

**O‘ZBEKISTON RESPUBLIKASI OLIY TA’LIM, FAN VA
INNOVATSIYALAR VAZIRLIGI
SIRDARYO VILOYATI HOKIMLIGI
GULISTON DAVLAT UNIVERSITETI,
TURKIYA RESPUBLIKASI BALIKESIR UNIVERSITETI,
TURKIYA RESPUBLIKASI FIRAT UNIVERSITETI,
YANGLING KASB-HUNAR VA TEXNIKA KOLLEJI**

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Mas’ul muharrirlar:

f.f.f.d. (PhD), dotsent A.Axrоров, f.f.d., professor F.Sharipov, f.f.d., professor I.Ermatov, f.f.n., dotsent J.Abdullayev, f.f.n., dotsent I.Pardayeva, f.f.f.d. (PhD), dotsent. M.Latipov, Prof. Dr. Banovsha Mammadova Guloghlana, Prof. Dr. Ertan Örgen, Prof. Dr. Suheyyla Demirkol Orak.

Tahrir hay’ati:

A.Axrоров, A.Mamatqulov, Sh.Ro‘ziqulov, Z.To‘ychiyeva

To‘plamga keltirilgan ma’ruza tezislarning mazmuni, undagi ma’lumotlar va me’yoriy hujjatlar hamda fikr-mulohazalar, takliflarning to‘g‘riligiga mualliflarning o‘zlari mas’uldirlar

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- O‘zbek tilining milliy korpusi yaratildi [<https://uzbekcorpus.uz/newIndex>];
- Elektron izohli lug‘atlar tuzildi [<https://www.izohli.uz/>];
- Avtomatlashtirilgan imlo tekshiruvchilar ishlab chiqildi [<https://savodxon.uz/>];
- Kompyuter lingvistikasi laboratoriyalari tashkil etildi.

Bu ishlar o‘zbek tilini raqamli muhitda keng qo‘llash, uni sun’iy intellekt asosida rivojlantirish uchun muhim poydevor bo‘lib xizmat qilmoqda.

Tilshunoslik fani tarixan boy an’anaga ega bo‘lib, har bir davrda o‘ziga xos yondashuvlar bilan boyib kelmoqda. XX asrda strukturalizm, generativ grammatika va kognitiv lingvistika nazariyalari fan rivojida katta burilish yasagan bo‘lsa, XXI asrda kompyuter lingvistikasi va korpus tadqiqotlari lingvistikani butunlay yangi bosqichga olib chiqdi.

Bugungi kunda tilshunoslik faqat nazariy fan emas, balki texnologik jarayonlarga ham bevosita ta’sir qiladigan amaliy sohaga aylanmoqda. Shu bois, tilshunoslikning yangi yondashuvlari va yutuqlarini o‘rganish nafaqat ilmiy, balki amaliy jihatdan ham katta ahamiyatga ega.

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METONYMY AS A MEANS OF FORMING NEW MEANINGS OF A WORD

Akhrorova Jamila Agzamovna,

FDU tayanch doktoranti

[**jamilaakhrorova@gmail.com**](mailto:jamilaakhrorova@gmail.com)

[**http://orcid.org/0009-0008-2591-2176**](http://orcid.org/0009-0008-2591-2176)

Abstract. The thesis below presents information about such concept as metonymic transference or in other words metonymy as a means of forming new semes. The observations and studies of linguists are given with obvious facts related the issue. Concrete approaches of linguists and the types of metonymic transference are presented with relevant examples.

Keywords: Metonymy, transference, cognitive, lexical-semantic, criteria, usual meaning, occasional meaning, concept, metaphor, seme.

The question of the causes and essence of metonymic transfers is interpreted differently because of a number of reasons, the first and foremost is the difference of points of view about identifying metonymic transferences. It is explained by the

existence of a number of approaches to considering this problem. The issue of identifying approaches to the study of metonymy cannot be considered solved. On the basis of analysis of literature on the given issue four main approaches can be presented on the main point of metonymy – cognitive, logical, psychological, and lexical-semantic. The first three approaches above are considered traditional, because they had been studied much earlier. At the end of the XX century as the cognitive approach appeared by the developing of cognitive science the concept of metonymy has only begun to be examined from the cognitive point of view. So as the term of metonymic transference is not considered as the historically widely studied concept, there are a number of points to be observed concretely.

Study and analysis of literature on the metonymic transference shows that their classification can be based on different criteria. The most common typology, apparently, may be considered the typology of metonymic transference which is associated with division of metonymy into usual and occasional.

The term “usual metonymy” was interpreted as the entire set of ideas that constitute the content of a given word for a member of a given linguistic community by German linguist H. Paul. [Пауль Г., 1960. С.96]

Usual or general language meanings of the word totally and metonymic in particular are called regular or lexicalized as well, since they are characterized by the regularity of occurrence, general acceptance, commonness and are reflected in dictionaries.[Некрасова Е., 1975. 128]

Under occasional meaning it can be interpreted those notions which the speaker connects with this word at the moment of speech and those notions which the listener connects particularly with this word too.

Occasional or individual meanings in metonymic transference are usage of the words in their figurative meaning, in other words, lexemes that has not become a lexeme of the vocabulary system of the language and that can not be seen in dictionaries. [Фомина 1990. 57-58]

The issue of metonymic transference has been in the center of discussion of many linguists and many of them presented their point of view relying on facts and samples. Representatives of logical direction such as L. Potebnya, P. P. Chauffeur J. J. Dubois and other linguists regard that on the basis of semantic transference of a word lies formal-logical relations between concepts, expressed by the words, which can be identified by the types of association, reflecting associations and capable of arising from the conscious of man. There are five of them: equivalence, exception or extraneousness, contradiction, subordination or inclusion, crossing or intersection. Thus A. Potebnya and a number of other linguists consider metaphor as exclusion of concepts, synecdoche as the result of including concepts and metonymy as the result of the intersection (crossing) of concepts. Potebnya interprets it as below: “If in the process of transference from the image to the meaning, the latter does not exclude the image, but on top of that (unlike synecdoche) it gets a new quality then it will be metonymy, This new quality can only occur because under concrete conditions accompanies in thought the image. [Потебня 1990. 182-186]

Other linguists who examined metonymic transference as J. Dubois confirm that the concept of replaceable and substitutable do not have common semantic relation, if on the basis of metaphor the semiotic intersection of two classes is assumed, then metonymy acts in the domain of non-overlapping classes [General rhetorics 1986, 213-219]. From the presented above we can conclude that as metonymy grasps two notions that are connected with each other with constant relations, its logical basis is the relation of inclusion.

The interpretation of the essence of metonymic transferences on the basis of componential analysis seems inaccurate due to many reasons. Firstly, the very selection of semes is accidental, because there are no concrete criteria by which the given process is performed. Besides, it is not always obvious to which extend should words be divided into their constituent components. As a result of the lack of a single criterion for choosing semes included in the words, the same material is interpreted differently, which can be the reason for ambiguity of metonymic transference.

It would be appropriate to state that all approaches mentioned above describe mechanism of metonymic transference, but it is not enough to explain and interpret the notion itself. The studies and observations reveal that the issue of metonymic transference still remains ambiguous and it requires more concrete investigations and facts to obtain entire developing of the problem.

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THE SYNTAX-SEMANTICS INTERFACE OF ELLIPSIS: ISSUES AND ANALYSES

**Nazarli Fidan Sadiq,
Müəllim**

**Email: nazarli.fidan1@gmail.com
Azerbaijan State Pedagogical University
ORCID: 0000-0002-4517-6048**

Abstract. This article explores the phenomenon of ellipsis at the syntax– semantics interface, emphasizing its structural, pragmatic, and functional significance